

ISic3483

I.Sicily inscription 3483

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific (?)

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Siracusa, Neapolis, from the foundations of a house on the circular piazza between the Agora and the Railway station

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 8462

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI336187

1. [— — — — — — — — — —]
2. [— —] κ,αὶ Εὐβουλ [— —]
3. [— —] Τ. □ υ (ἰὸς) □ Σεουῆρ [ος]
4. [διδά]σκαλος vac.
5. [— — υ(ἰὸς)] □ Σπερκια [νὸς(?)]
6. [σαλπι] κτής (?) □ vac.
7. [ὁ δεῖνα υ(ἰὸς)] Ἄφρικ [ανὸς(?)]
8. [κιθαρι]σ [τῆς(?)]
9. [— — — — — — — — — —]
- 10.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645104

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Bibliography

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undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

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